

EFFECTIVE DISPERSION OF GRAPHENE IN THERMOPLASTIC POLYMERS: CHEMICAL AND PROCESSING STRATEGIES

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ABSTRACT

In this work we present a series of strategies to obtain thermoplastic/graphene nanocomposites with improved electrical, thermal and mechanical properties, based on changes induced during the process of nanocomposites preparation, i.e. chemical functionalization of graphene, covalent connection of graphene and polymers and processing methods.

In the case of polyethylene, PE a combination of chemical functionalization of graphene with short-chain PE along with a two-step component blending process (that we denominate the “gradient interphase” approach) was employed to obtain PE-graphene nanocomposites with good thermal and electrical conductivity.

The case of the thermoplastic elastomer poly (styrene-ethylene butylene-styrene), SEBS is particularly interesting since the morphology and phase distribution of the nanocomposites strongly depend on the characteristics of the graphene used (unmodified or modified). With unmodified graphene, in the nanocomposites both components segregate into two phases, and films produced display a conductive face and an insulating one. However, graphene functionalized with short-polymer chains show improved dispersion in SEBS leading to more homogeneous materials that display transversal conductivity. We will show that with appropriate functionalization graphene can be directed to specific domains in SEBS.

Finally, the case of poly (vinylidene fluoride), PVDF, is also addressed and functionalized graphene is employed to favor the formation of β -crystals in PVDF, which are directly associated to the piezo-electric effect.

1. INTRODUCTION

It has been suggested that graphene will be the most important material in the coming years since it reunites several outstanding properties never before observed in a single material, such as remarkably high electron mobility at room temperature, superior strength, high thermal conductivity, optical transparency, impermeability, high surface area and so on. From the point of view of polymer nanocomposites these properties make graphene an ideal candidate to be used as a filler [1].

Effective dispersion of graphene in polymeric matrices is of paramount importance to obtain materials with substantially improved properties. The driving force behind this is to obtain a strong interface between both components [1,2].

To incorporate graphene into, or compatibilize with, polymers it must be appropriately modified in order to provide it with adequate functional groups able to interact with specific chemical moieties in polymeric matrices, and then subsequently mixed with the polymer. This is the typical strategy employed for the preparation of graphene-based PNCs. However, the interactions obtained in this case are of a supramolecular-type and could lead to segregation of components during continuous use, limiting or worsening the materials durability.

In our laboratory we have explored two alternative routes based on the covalent incorporation of graphene into polymers [3,4,5] and the decoration of graphene with short polymer brushes that are used as fillers in compatible high molecular weight polymers [6,7]. In the first case, stable dispersions of graphene can be achieved in the matrix that lead to durable materials with adequate control of the microstructure of the nanocomposites. However, sometimes the covalent attachment of graphene to the polymer may be detrimental to specific properties, especially those related to the movement of electrons or phonons. Meanwhile, in the second case the interface obtained is not as strong as the previous case, but a high density of points of interaction with the matrix is assured, by means of the grafted short-polymer chains.

The case of nanocomposites of thermoplastic polymers like PE, SEBS or PVDF filled with graphene, a major challenge exists because, in most cases, simply mixing the components does not guarantee the existence of effective interfacial interactions. In this work we present a series of strategies to prepare thermoplastic/graphene nanocomposites with improved electrical, thermal and mechanical properties.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section is divided into three parts according to the thermoplastic polymer employed.

2.1 High density polyethylene (HDPE)

Graphene was modified with short-chain polyethylene brushes by thiol-ene click reaction as follows: 0.5 g of PE-SH was dissolved in 50 mL of anhydrous *o*-DCB, under a nitrogen atmosphere. Subsequently, a thermal-initiator (AIBN 1.72 g, 0.01 mol) and graphene (0.5 g) were added to the polymer solution. The mixture was heated at 70 °C and stirred overnight. The solid product was collected by filtration and washed with abundant amounts of methanol and hot toluene to remove excess initiator and non-reacted polymer, respectively.

This modified graphene was employed to prepare HDPE nanocomposites following two different processes. In the first method the nanocomposite was prepared in two steps. The first step involved the mixing of modified graphene with short chain polyethylene (PE-OH) in a 50/50 ratio in warm xylene and subsequent precipitation in methanol and drying. This mixture was used as filler of HDPE in the second step. For this purpose fillers were mixed with HDPE in xylene in order to obtain nanocomposites with final filler content of ca. 1%. The mixtures were then precipitated with methanol, and dried under vacuum. The second route involves a direct mixing of modified graphene and HDPE in warm xylene solution, followed by precipitation, drying and compounding in an extruder.

2.2. Poly(styrene-*b*-ethylene-co-butylene-*b*-styrene) (SEBS)

Graphene modified as described for HDPE was also employed as filler for the SEBS triblock copolymer. The nanocomposites were prepared by mixing in *o*-dichlorobenzene appropriate amounts of SEBS and modified-graphene in order to obtain nanocomposites with different compositions. Films of all nanocomposites were prepared by controlled evaporation of the solvent.

2.3. Poly(vinylidene fluoride).

Graphene oxide (GO) was modified using a different procedure to that employed in the previous examples, incorporating hydrophobic chains by esterification with octadecylalcohol. Briefly, 200 mg of GO were dispersed in 50 mL of *N,N'*-dymethylformamide with ultrasounds. Subsequently the

reagent (1 g., 3.7 mmol) and the catalyst system, DCC (5 g, 24.2 mmol) and DMAP (0.35 g, 2.9 mmol) were added and the reaction mixture maintained under magnetic stirring at 40 °C for three days

Nanocomposites with PVFD of different compositions were prepared by mixing appropriate amounts of modified GO and the polymer in DMF at 60 °C by 3 h and precipitation with methanol.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nanocomposites of appropriately modified graphene with three different thermoplastic polymers have been prepared, namely HDPE, SEBS and PVDF. Graphene has been modified with short-polymer chains in order to obtain polymer brushes emerging from the graphene surface. In principle, these brushes strongly interact with polymeric chains of similar nature. In other words, the grafted chains penetrates the polymer matrix generating a great number of interactions that, despite are supramolecular in nature, assure a strong graphene/polymer interface (Figure 1A).

Due to the differences between the characteristics, the results on each matrix are presented and discussed separately.

3.1. HDPE

This matrix is perhaps one of the most challenging when graphene-based nanocomposites with superior properties are pursued. In fact, among the vast bibliography in polymeric nanocomposites with graphene, the case of HDPE occupies a very small part. [8]

Figure 1. (A) Schematic illustration of the interaction between short polymer brushes and bulk polymer in G-HDPE. (B) Image of the nanocomposite as obtained (B) and after hot-pressing (C). SEM images of cryofractured G-HDPE with 1 wt. % of graphene. Graph of the variation of the electrical conductivity of G- HDPE with graphene content (E).

As stated in the experimental section we use graphene functionalized with short-chain polyethylene brushes to prepare HDPE/graphene nanocomposites with better properties. In the first methodology the nanocomposites are prepared by solution blending. The solid greyish material (Figure 1 B) can be converted to the flexible films in Figure 1C by hot-pressing. In order to determine the degree of graphene dispersion in the HDPE matrix, SEM was employed, which showed that the graphene laminates appear to be perfectly dispersed in the polymer matrix (Figure 1D). This good dispersion of the filler in the matrix is responsible for improvements in electrical and mechanical properties.

Especially interesting is the case of the electrical conductivity where it can be noted that very little graphene (approx. 0.4-0.8 wt. %) ensures percolation pathways that raise the conductivity of HDPE several orders of magnitude. Moreover, very good results are obtained in terms of absolute conductivity values as, for instance, the sample containing around 2 wt. % of graphene reaches $\sim 0.02 \text{ S.cm}^{-1}$.

These improvements in the electrical properties are accompanied by little or no change in the mechanical properties of the films or in the thermal stability. Regarding the Young's modulus, changes are minimal, the value for the nanocomposite being slightly lower than that for the pure polymer. The values are 630 ± 30 and 587 ± 29 for HDPE and HDPE-G, respectively. With respect to the elongation at break, a plasticizing effect is observed using click modified graphene because of the action of the short-chain. However, it must be pointed out that the nanocomposite with the modified graphene displays a value higher than that of the pure HDPE. The elongation at break presents values of 535 ± 27 and 703 ± 35 for HDPE and HDPE-G, respectively.

This procedure has been extended to samples prepared by melt compounding and the properties are under evaluation. However, preliminary results suggest a new ability of G-HDPE films as a significant diminution on the gas permeation has recently been observed.

3.2. SEBS

Thermoplastic elastomers like SEBS triblock copolymers constitute a special family of copolymers since they display the physical properties of rubbers but can be processed as thermoplastics. However, the investigation on the incorporation of graphene into a SEBS matrix is limited to a handful of examples and advances are so far only modest.[9]

Generally, the styrenic phase has been used as the target to incorporate graphene in SEBS, because of π - π graphene/styrene interactions and only improvements in mechanical properties have been achieved.[9] However, in order to achieve new specific properties like electrical conductivity it would be interesting to locate the graphene in the ethylene phase of SEBS.

In this study we use the graphene modified with short- PE brushes to reinforce SEBS, with the objective to selectively incorporate the graphene into the ethylene phase. After blending in solution films are prepared by drop casting (Figure 2A). These films are highly flexible even with high contents of graphene (Figure 2B). The modified graphene dispersed very well in the matrix, as shown by SEM images (Figure 2C-D). In addition, the AFM experiments suggest that the morphology of the copolymer is altered by the presence of graphene. It can be seen that the original cylindrical styrenic phase in pure SEBS change to a more laminar morphology with 1 wt. % of graphene (Figure 2E-F). The effects of modified graphene on the polymer morphology will be deeply studied by XRD using synchrotron radiation.

Figure 2. Photograph of G-SEBS 2 wt.% drop casted film as obtained (A) and under bending (B). SEM images of SEBS (C) and G-SEBS 1 wt. % (D). AFM phase image of SEBS (E) and G-SEBS 1 wt.% (F) .

Regarding properties, four-probe measurements display a typical percolation behavior, where the electrical conductivity suddenly increases for a specific amount of graphene, in this case between 2-2,5 wt. %. This percolation threshold is somewhat higher than in other polymer nanocomposites and the absolute values are slightly lower than those observed for other polymers. The reasons for these observations have to be determined.

3.3. PVDF

Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) is an important polymer having piezo and pyroelectric properties. It exhibits five different crystalline polymorphic structures (α , β , γ , δ , ϵ) of which β polymorph is piezoelectrically active.¹⁰

It has been proposed that nanocomposites of PVDF with exfoliated graphene (EG) and with functionalized graphene sheet (FG) pure β and a mixture of α and β polymorphs are produced with the former and the later, respectively.[11] In this study we used graphene oxide grafted with long alkyl hydrophobic chains. By means of this system we seek a different GO/polymer interaction, i.e. van der Waals interactions between the grafted chains and the PVDF and covalent bonding between polar groups in GO and fluorine atoms in the polymer.

Figure 3. FTIR (A) and DSC melting scan (B) of PVDF and its nanocomposites with GO.

We have investigated the formation of the different polymorphs in PVDF as a function of the amount of GO by using FTIR, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and X-ray diffraction. Preliminary results show slight influence of GO concentration on the crystalline structure of PVDF in the nanocomposites. In addition, it seems that effects of the processing conditions over the polymorphism are more important than the presence of functionalized GO (Figure 3 AB). Further details of the properties of these nanocomposites will be presented.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The importance of the chemical control of the graphene surface on the properties of a series of different thermoplastic polymer has been discussed, and it has been demonstrated that the grafting of polymer brushes strongly improves the interactions between graphene and different types of polymers. By means of this strategy very good electrical conductivity is obtained in a commodity polymer like HDPE and one of the most important thermoplastic elastomers, SEBS.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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